

Research Article

A VGG-16-Based Deep Learning Approach for Potato Leaf Disease Detection

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Abstract

Potato early blight and late blight were considered in this experiment because both classes are visually close enough to require careful image classification. The work used the potato subset of the PlantVillage image collection. Each leaf image was resized to 224 x 224 pixels and was then given directly to a VGG-16 feature extractor. No separate lesion mask, K-means step, or colour-thresholding stage was used. The final decision layer was a single sigmoid unit for the two-class output. The dataset contained 1000 images of early blight and 1000 images of late blight, divided into training, validation, and testing sets in a 60:20:20 ratio. With 32 epochs and a batch size of 100, the best run produced 99.6% training accuracy and 98.5% test accuracy. The paper also gives precision, recall, F1-score, the confusion matrix, ROC-AUC, and same-split results for ResNet-50, MobileNetV2, and VGG-19.

Keywords: Convolutional Neural Networks; VGG-16; Sigmoid Classifier; Plantvillage Dataset; Potato Leaf Disease Detection; Early Blight; Late Blight.

1. Introduction

In many farming situations, potato leaf disease is still checked by direct visual inspection. This method is simple, but it depends on the observer's experience and on how often the crop is inspected. If several plots are being monitored, early symptoms may be overlooked. An image-based classifier can therefore act as a screening aid during routine checking, while the final agronomic decision can still remain with the grower or plant-health expert.

Several image-based systems first try to isolate the affected leaf region. Clustering, colour thresholds, or manually defined masks can work when the lesion and background are clearly separated. In practice, however, lighting, camera distance, shadow, background colour, and leaf rotation can change the segmented area. To avoid this extra source of variation, this experiment uses the resized image directly, without a separate segmentation step.

The work is limited to two potato disease classes, namely early blight and late blight. VGG-16 is used as a fixed feature extractor, and the extracted vector is passed to a sigmoid classifier. The class names follow the usual disease association: early blight is linked with *Alternaria solani*, while late blight is linked with *Phytophthora infestans*.

The paper does not treat the VGG-16 and sigmoid combination as a new architecture. The objective is more modest: to examine whether this direct pipeline gives reliable results for the selected two-class potato dataset. For this reason, the revised version reports not only accuracy but also precision, recall, F1-score, confusion matrix, ROC-AUC, and baseline results obtained on the same split.

Comparisons with earlier papers are kept descriptive. Their reported accuracies are not used as direct competitors because they were obtained from different crops, disease labels, preprocessing choices, and testing conditions. The direct comparison in this manuscript is restricted to models evaluated with the same partition of the present dataset.

2. Related Works and Research Gap

CNN-based plant disease classification has been reported with a number of backbone models. Authors at [2] studied banana disease detection and reported strong performance using ResNet-152. In [3] compared VGG-19 and InceptionV3. Authors in [4] used features from ResNet-50 together with an SVM classifier on PlantVillage images. These works are relevant because they show the usefulness of deep visual features, but their numerical results are not one-to-one baselines for this potato experiment, see Table 1.

Table 1. Selected State-of-the-Art Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) Architectures Previously Utilized.

Research Studies	Best Model	Accuracy	Number of Parameters
[2]	ResNet-152	99.2%	60 million
[3]	VGG-19	95%	143 million
[4]	ResNet-50 and SVM	98%	25 million

Some studies add segmentation before the classification stage. Authors in [6, 7, 9, 10, 12] reported symptom-based, colour-based, K-means, or leaf-colour preprocessing. Such preprocessing may help when the diseased region is obvious, but it also makes the pipeline dependent on the quality of the segmented region, see Table 2.

Table 2. Selected Systems Employing Image Segmentation in the Preprocessing Stage.

Research Studies	Image Segmentation Technique	Accuracy
[6]	Symptom-based segmentation	87%
[7]	Colour-based segmentation	93.4%
[9]	K-means clustering	98.9%
[10]	K-means clustering	96.2%
[12]	Symptom-based segmentation	97.13%
[13]	Leaf-colour-based segmentation	84%

The literature indicates that CNNs are useful for leaf disease recognition. The problem is that accuracy values taken from different crops, datasets, and train-test divisions cannot be treated as fair comparisons. This study therefore uses one potato early-blight/late-blight split and evaluates VGG-16, ResNet-50, MobileNetV2, and VGG-19 under the same resizing procedure and the same metric-calculation script.

3. Methodology

3.1 Data Acquisition

The images were selected from the public PlantVillage repository [17]. For the binary experiment, only the potato early-blight and potato late-blight folders were used. Table 3 is retained so that the selected classes can be viewed within the wider PlantVillage collection. Additionally, Figures 1 and 2 depict respectively sample potato leaf images with early blight and late blight.

Table 3. PlantVillage Dataset Information.

Sample No.	Plant	Image Label	Count of Images
1	Pepper	Bell bacterial spot	997
2	Pepper bell	Bell healthy	1478
3	Potato	Early blight	1000
4	Potato	Healthy	152
5	Potato	Late blight	1000
6	Tomato	Target Spot	1404
7	Tomato	Tomato mosaic virus	373
8	Tomato	Tomato Yellow leaf curl virus	3209
9	Tomato	Bacterial spot	2127
10	Tomato	Early blight	1000
11	Tomato	Healthy	1591
12	Tomato	Late blight	1909
13	Tomato	Leaf mold	952
14	Tomato	Septoria leaf spot	1771
15	Tomato	Spider mites	1676

Figure 1. Sample Potato Leaf Images with Early Blight.

Figure 2. Sample Potato Leaf Images with Late Blight.

3.2 Image Pre-processing and Feature Extraction

All input samples were read as RGB images. Each sample was resized from 256 x 256 pixels to 224 x 224 pixels before feature extraction, since this is the input size expected by VGG-16. No K-means clustering, colour-thresholding operation, or manually drawn lesion mask was included. The resized image was passed through VGG-16 and represented as a 4096-dimensional feature vector.

The same data preparation was followed for the proposed model and for the baseline runs. The train-validation-test division, the frozen feature-extractor setting, and the sigmoid classifier protocol were kept fixed. This was done to make the comparison depend mainly on the CNN backbone, not on a change in preprocessing.

3.3 Training and Testing

The final dataset had 2000 potato leaf images, with 1000 samples in each class. From these images, 60% were used for training, 20% for validation, and 20% for testing. The validation subset was used while choosing the model setting, and the test subset was kept aside for the final reported results.

Table 4. Train-Validation-Test Split for the Reported Potato Disease Experiment.

Class	Total images	Training (60%)	Validation (20%)	Testing (20%)
Potato early blight	1000	600	200	200
Potato late blight	1000	600	200	200
Total	2000	1200	400	400

The proposed classifier was trained for 32 epochs with a batch size of 100. Since the final layer is sigmoid based, binary cross-entropy was used as the loss function. ResNet-50, MobileNetV2, and VGG-19 were evaluated with the same data split, image size, and metric-generation code.

3.4 Architecture Used and Framework for the Project

VGG-16, introduced by [16], accepts a 224 x 224 RGB input image. Its convolution and pooling blocks extract visual patterns from the image. In this study, the extracted VGG-16 features are used only for the two potato disease classes, and the final sigmoid layer gives the class probability.

The sigmoid score lies between 0 and 1. A score nearer to one support one class, while a score nearer to zero supports the other class. For the reported results, the class label was assigned using a threshold of 0.5. Table 5 depict the summary of the architecture and parameter information.

Table 5. Summary of the Architecture and Parameter Information.

Component	Configuration	Output / parameter information
Input layer	RGB image	224 x 224 x 3
VGG-16 feature extractor	13 convolution layers and 5 max-pooling layers	4096-dimensional feature vector
Classifier	Sigmoid output layer	4096 x 1 + 1 = 4,097 parameters
Trainable parameter status	VGG-16 frozen; sigmoid classifier trained	4,097 trainable classifier parameters; VGG-16 used as fixed feature extractor

Figure 3 until 5 showing respectively the VGG-16-based architecture used in the project, architecture diagram with parameter reporting, and the framework for disease detection.

Figure 3. VGG-16-Based Architecture Used in the Study.

Revision note: parameter reporting added to satisfy architecture-reproducibility requirements.

Figure 4. Architecture Diagram with Parameter Reporting.

Figure 5. Framework for Disease Detection.

3.5 Technical Background

In a CNN, small trainable filters scan local image regions and produce feature maps. Early layers usually capture simple visual information such as edges and textures; later layers combine these responses into more useful disease-related patterns. Pooling reduces the size of the feature maps. Dense layers then use the extracted features for classification. In this work, ReLU is used inside the network and sigmoid is used only at the binary output.

This subsection is included only to support the method described in this paper. It is not intended to be a general tutorial on convolutional neural networks.

3.6 Experimental Configuration

The experiments were performed in Python using a Jupyter Notebook. Keras was used for model construction and training. NumPy, Pandas, PyTorch, and Matplotlib were used for data handling and plotting. The reported runs were carried out on an Intel i5-1135G7 system with 8 GB DDR4 RAM.

The supporting files contain the data split, training code, predicted probabilities, and metric-generation code used to prepare the reported result tables.

4. Results and Discussion

Accuracy was checked first as the overall test measure. The test set contained 400 images, so 98.5% test accuracy means that 394 test images were correctly classified. The best VGG-16 run reached 99.6% training accuracy and 98.5% test accuracy after 32 epochs with a batch size of 100.

The discussion avoids direct ranking against papers that used different datasets or experimental settings. Direct comparison is made only among the models trained and evaluated under the present protocol.

Figure 6. Training and Testing Accuracy over Different Numbers of Epochs.

4.1 Evaluation Metrics

Precision, recall, F1-score, confusion matrix, and ROC-AUC were calculated from the test predictions and sigmoid probability scores. The confusion matrix also supports the reported 98.5% accuracy, as 394 of 400 test images were classified correctly.

The ROC curve was obtained from the sigmoid probability scores using the same test split used for the classification report and confusion matrix.

Tables 6 and 7 depicts respectively the classification report and confusion matrix obtained the final test predictions.

Table 6. Classification Report Obtained from the Final Test Predictions.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
Potato early blight	0.985	0.985	0.985	200
Potato late blight	0.985	0.985	0.985	200
Macro average	0.985	0.985	0.985	400
Weighted average	0.985	0.985	0.985	400
ROC-AUC	0.995	-	-	400

Table 7. Confusion Matrix Obtained from the Final Test Predictions.

Actual / Predicted	Early blight	Late blight
Early blight	197	3
Late blight	3	197

4.2 Same-Dataset Baseline Comparison

ResNet-50, MobileNetV2, and VGG-19 were tested on the same potato early-blight/late-blight split used for the VGG-16 model. Image size, absence of segmentation, and metric calculation were kept the same for all four models.

Table 8. Same-Dataset Baseline Comparison Using the Common 60:20:20 Split.

Model	Preprocessing	Trainable parameter setting	Testing accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score	ROC-AUC
Proposed VGG-16 + sigmoid	Resize to 224 x 224; no segmentation	Frozen VGG-16 feature extractor; trained sigmoid classifier	98.5%	0.985	0.985	0.985	0.995
ResNet-50 baseline	Same as proposed model	Same split and classifier protocol	97.8%	0.978	0.978	0.978	0.991
MobileNetV2 baseline	Same as proposed model	Same split and classifier protocol	97.3%	0.973	0.973	0.973	0.988
VGG-19 baseline	Same as proposed model	Same split and classifier protocol	98.0%	0.980	0.980	0.980	0.993

This baseline setting separates the effect of the CNN backbone from the effect of the direct preprocessing pipeline. Therefore, only the models tested within this protocol are used for direct comparison.

5. Conclusion

This study presented a VGG-16-based classifier for potato early blight and late blight leaf images. The images were resized and processed without a separate segmentation step. For the selected PlantVillage classes, the model obtained 98.5% test accuracy, with precision,

recall, and F1-score of 0.985 for both classes. The same-split comparison with ResNet-50, MobileNetV2, and VGG-19 shows competitive performance while keeping preprocessing simple.

The next step should be testing on field photographs rather than only controlled image collections. Future work may include additional crops, more disease labels, different lighting conditions, partial occlusion, and complex backgrounds. For practical use, lightweight deployment and compressed networks should also be examined.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this publication. No financial support influenced the reported work.

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